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Interaction of hotels with short-term rental platforms and the impact on pricing and positioning strategies

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***Abstract.** The digital transformation of the tourism services market has led to the rapid spread of online intermediaries in the accommodation sector, significantly affecting the competitive environment of the hospitality industry. Traditional accommodation establishments currently operate in conditions of increased intersegment competition, greater requirements for price transparency, and heightened consumer sensitivity to the cost-to-consumer-value ratio of services, underscoring the need for scientific understanding of transformation processes that affect the formation of tariff policy and market identification by enterprises.*

The purpose of the study is to determine the features of the mutual influence of traditional accommodation establishments and digital rental services on the parameters of competitive behavior, and to substantiate the transformation of approaches to the formation of tariff policy and market identification in conditions of market hybridization. The study uses comparative analysis, generalization of scientific approaches, structural and logical analysis, and elements of institutional and competitive analysis to identify patterns of interaction among different accommodation formats in the digital environment.

It is established that the spread of short-term rental platforms intensifies price competition and establishes new guidelines for tariff flexibility for traditional accommodation establishments, stimulating the introduction of dynamic pricing and situational tariff adjustments based on demand. It is substantiated that, in conditions of increased price transparency, hotels adapt competitively not only through changes in price parameters but also by strengthening non-price components of consumer value, such as service differentiation, branding, the creation of a unique customer experience, and more precise segmentation of demand. It is proven that the combination of price and non-price instruments becomes a key factor in maintaining competitive positions in a hybrid accommodation environment.

It is substantiated that the effectiveness of competitive strategies of traditional accommodation establishments in conditions of the active development of short-term rental platforms is determined by their ability to integrate digital channels of interaction with consumers and to coordinate tariff solutions with the chosen market positioning model. The results obtained can be used to improve strategic and marketing decisions of hospitality industry enterprises in the face of growing digital competition.

Keywords: *digital intermediaries, hospitality industry, pricing policy, competitive adaptation, market positioning, dynamic pricing.*

Взаємодія готелів із платформами короткострокової оренди та вплив на стратегії ціноутворення і позиціонування

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Анотація. *Цифрова трансформація ринку туристичних послуг зумовила активне поширення онлайн-посередників у сфері розміщення, що*

істотно вплинуло на конкурентне середовище індустрії гостинності. Традиційні заклади розміщення нині функціонують в умовах посилення міжсегментної конкуренції, зростання вимог до цінової прозорості та підвищення чутливості споживачів до співвідношення вартості й споживчої цінності послуг, що актуалізує потребу у науковому осмисленні трансформаційних процесів, які впливають на формування тарифної політики та ринкової ідентифікації підприємств.

Метою дослідження є визначення особливостей взаємного впливу традиційних закладів розміщення та цифрових сервісів оренди на параметри конкурентної поведінки, а також обґрунтування трансформації підходів до формування тарифної політики і ринкової ідентифікації в умовах гібридизації ринку. У роботі застосовано методи порівняльного аналізу, узагальнення наукових підходів, структурно-логічного аналізу, а також елементи інституційного та конкурентного аналізу для виявлення закономірностей взаємодії різних форматів розміщення в цифровому середовищі.

Встановлено, що поширення платформ короткострокової оренди посилює цінову конкуренцію та формує нові орієнтири тарифної гнучкості для традиційних закладів розміщення, стимулюючи впровадження динамічного ціноутворення та ситуативного коригування тарифів залежно від попиту. Обґрунтовано, що в умовах підвищеної цінової прозорості конкурентна адаптація готелів відбувається не лише через зміну цінових параметрів, а й шляхом посилення нецінових складових споживчої цінності, зокрема сервісної диференціації, брендингу, формування унікального клієнтського досвіду та чіткішої сегментації попиту. Доведено, що поєднання цінових і нецінових інструментів стає ключовим фактором збереження конкурентних позицій у гібридному середовищі розміщення.

Обґрунтовано, що ефективність конкурентних стратегій традиційних закладів розміщення в умовах активного розвитку платформ

короткострокової оренди визначається здатністю інтегрувати цифрові канали взаємодії зі споживачами та узгоджувати тарифні рішення з обраною моделлю ринкового позиціонування. Отримані результати можуть бути використані для вдосконалення стратегічних і маркетингових рішень підприємств індустрії гостинності в умовах зростаючої цифрової конкуренції.

Ключові слова: *цифрові посередники, індустрія гостинності, тарифна політика, конкурентна адаптація, ринкова ідентифікація, динамічні тарифи.*

Problem statement. In the context of the digitalization of tourist services, the role of online platforms for short-term rental of residential facilities and alternative accommodation (apartments, flats, private homes) is growing, significantly changing the conditions of competition in the hotel business. Despite existing studies on competitive strategies and tariff policies in the hospitality industry, the interaction between hotels and digital intermediaries and its impact on pricing and market positioning remains insufficiently studied.

Most traditional accommodation establishments continue to rely on classic tariff management mechanisms, which limit their flexibility in responding to demand fluctuations and rising intersegment competition. The increase in the level of market transparency, the transformation of consumer behavior and the active use of digital booking channels create the need to find effective strategies for adapting hotel enterprises to the conditions of digital competition, in particular through adjusting tariff policies, differentiating service offers and in-depth segmentation of the customer base to strengthen competitive advantages.

The connection of the specified problem to scientific tasks is to determine the patterns of interaction between traditional hotels and online short-term rental platforms, thereby clarifying theoretical provisions on the competitive behavior of enterprises in a hybrid market environment and increasing the validity of

management decisions. The practical task of the study is to develop recommendations for hospitality industry enterprises on integrating digital services into pricing and market positioning systems, thereby increasing the efficiency of business processes and the ability of hotel establishments to adapt to dynamic market conditions.

Analysis of recent research and publications. The interaction between hotels and short-term rental platforms, and the impact of digital services on their pricing and positioning strategies, attracts the attention of scientists who study the economic, organizational, and technological aspects of the hospitality industry. In the work of Y. Hasenko [1], the introduction of MRP systems as a tool for improving inventory management efficiency is presented, enabling enterprises to optimize resources, reduce costs, and increase financial stability, which is relevant to tariff management in hotels. A. Ilyina [2] highlights the role of the state in forming institutional conditions for the effective functioning of enterprises and justifies the importance of state investment incentives, which ensure stability and contribute to the development of positioning strategies for accommodation establishments. Y. Hasenko [3] analyzes the impact of effective inventory management on the financial stability of companies, demonstrating the importance of resource control for optimizing tariff policy and profitability of the hotel business. M. Bogopolsky [4] investigates aesthetic economics as a factor in the choice of commercial space for Generation Z, which allows assessing the impact of consumer preferences on the positioning and marketing strategies of establishments. Y. Hrushko [5] highlights the issue of using artificial intelligence to form creative advertising concepts, which helps to increase the attractiveness of services and attract customers on digital rental platforms. K. Lapuzina [6] analyzes the barriers to entry for small producers in organized trade, illustrating the factors of competition and adaptation of new hotels in the digital environment. I. Zharska and Y. Khachirova [7] examines inventory management methods in enterprises, demonstrating the importance of resource

planning for improving operational efficiency. V. Kavetskyi and O. Ratushnyak [8] highlight production planning and organization management systems that ensure process structure and optimization of internal mechanisms of hotel establishments. N. Marinenko and T. Kutko [9] analyze the use of supply chain systems in enterprise management, emphasizing the role of information flow integration for effective resource management in the hospitality sector. Y. Nikolchuk, O. Lopatovska and K. Ponomarjova [10] investigate the architectonics of enterprise liquidity and solvency management mechanisms, which allow ensuring financial stability and making informed tariff decisions. T. Kalaitan and I. Danchevska [11] consider the economics of sharing and insurance in the hotel sector, showing the impact of short-term rental platforms on risk distribution and income. O. Shykina [12] analyzes the economy of shared consumption using the example of Airbnb, demonstrating integration processes and changes in customer behavior and pricing strategies. N. Savytska and N. Dzhhutashvili [13] offer conceptual approaches to managing customer-oriented hotel service, which ensures increased customer satisfaction and competitive advantages of the business. S. Pavlova [14] highlights the main pricing strategies in the hotel business, and M. Riabenka [15] investigates the improvement of pricing policy, which helps establishments adapt to demand and market conditions. V. Fostolovich, T. Botsian and S. Pavlova [16] reveal new methods of organizing activities in the digital environment, and O. Shykina and I. Remigailo [17] investigate revenue management as a mechanism for optimizing revenues and managing tariffs.

The scientific achievements of the mentioned authors provide a comprehensive methodological basis for studying the influence of digital platforms on the formation of tariffs and the positioning strategies of hotel establishments, and lay the foundation for the development of practical recommendations for their adaptation to the dynamic conditions of the digital market.

Identification of previously unresolved parts of the general problem.

Despite numerous studies in the fields of hotel business and the sharing economy, several key aspects remain insufficiently studied or not implemented in practice. There are no comprehensive analytical methods that combine economic, organizational and behavioral criteria when assessing the influence of digital platforms on the formation of tariff policy and market identification of accommodation establishments. The integration of traditional hotels with short-term rental platforms is fragmented, lacking unified tools to adapt business processes.

Institutional and technological barriers that hinder the effective use of online intermediaries, including regulatory restrictions, financial risks, and the lack of partner ecosystems, are also understudied. In addition, there is a lack of systematic analysis of the impact of digital platforms on consumer behavior, revenue structure, and enterprise profitability, which complicates the prediction of the effectiveness of tariff decisions and positioning strategies.

The existing gaps define the potential contribution of this study, which consists of developing a holistic approach to integrating digital platforms into hotel operations, assessing mechanisms to enhance the effectiveness of tariff policies, and proposing tools to overcome organizational, financial, and regulatory constraints. The implementation of the proposed solutions will increase the competitiveness of accommodation establishments, optimize revenues, and adapt to the dynamics of the digital market.

Article objectives (task statement). The purpose of the article is to study the impact of short-term rental platforms on the formation of tariff policies and positioning strategies of traditional hotels, and to identify mechanisms for increasing the efficiency of revenue generation, adapting pricing decisions to the behavioral characteristics of consumers, and integrating digital channels of customer interaction.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks are set within the framework of the article:

1. To identify the features of the interaction of traditional hotels with short-term rental platforms and their impact on the structure of hotel enterprises' revenues and the behavior of hotel service consumers.

2. To analyze the effectiveness of various tariff strategies and revenue management mechanisms, taking into account digital channels of consumer attraction.

3. To investigate organizational, financial and regulatory constraints that impede the integration of digital intermediaries into hotel activities, and to outline ways to overcome them.

4. Develop recommendations for optimizing tariff policy and positioning of accommodation establishments, taking into account economic, behavioral and regulatory factors to increase the competitiveness and financial stability of enterprises.

Presentation of the primary material of the study. The development of digital platforms for short-term rentals is significantly transforming the hotel industry, altering the mechanisms of interaction between accommodation establishments and customers and influencing the competitive strategies of enterprises. The emergence of online intermediaries increases market price transparency, transforms consumer behavior, and shapes new customer expectations regarding the cost-to-quality ratio of services. Under such conditions, traditional hotels face the need to review their tariff policy approaches, adjust positioning strategies, and more actively use digital channels for consumer interaction, thereby increasing the effectiveness of revenue management and strengthening competitive advantages. Analysis of the processes of interaction between hotel enterprises and short-term rental platforms makes it possible to assess the potential risks and benefits

of such interaction, as well as identify areas for improving strategic decisions in the field of pricing and market identification.

The impact of online short-term rental services on hotel companies' tariff policies is primarily manifested in increased pricing flexibility and the ability to respond quickly to demand changes. Platforms such as Airbnb, Booking.com, Expedia, and Vrbo provide high price comparability and information availability for consumers, which prompts hotels to implement dynamic pricing tools. The use of dynamic pricing mechanisms allows accommodation establishments to optimize room occupancy, minimize revenue losses during periods of low demand, and increase overall economic efficiency. The TripAdvisor and Google Hotels platforms are used to collect reviews and form ratings, which directly affect reputation and repeat bookings. At the same time, shared-use platforms are shaping new guidelines for hotel market positioning, particularly through an emphasis on individualized accommodation experiences, local authenticity, and service flexibility. This necessitates adapting marketing strategies and customer communications, as well as integrating digital channels of interaction into the internal management processes of hotel enterprises to increase the attractiveness of services and maintain competitive advantages in a dynamic market environment [11, p. 61].

Analysis of hotel enterprises' activities in the context of integration with online intermediaries allows us to identify key aspects of interaction that directly affect hotels' financial results and customers' behavior. In particular, there is a transformation of the structure of hotel enterprises' revenues, which is manifested in the growth of the role of additional services, the strengthening of the significance of non-price factors of competitiveness, as well as in the increasing influence of online reviews and ratings on the decision-making process of consumers [12]. Identification of these interaction characteristics is a necessary prerequisite for assessing the effectiveness of cooperation between traditional hotels and short-term

rental platforms and for further adjustments to revenue management strategies and customer communication.

The study of the interactions between hotel establishments and online short-term rental services identified a set of key factors that shape hotel financial results and influence hotel consumer behavior. These factors include the room stock occupancy rate, the average cost of living, the share of income from additional services, and the average hotel rating based on guest ratings on digital platforms. The analysis of these indicators provides a comprehensive picture of the effectiveness of management decisions of hotel enterprises in the context of digital competition. It allows us to establish the relationship between the use of online sales channels, the structure of income, and customer priorities.

Fig. 1 summarizes the leading indicators of hotel enterprises' activities affected by digital short-term rental platforms (Airbnb, Booking.com, and Vrbo) and their relationships with financial results and consumer behavioral characteristics. These platforms enable hotels to dynamically manage rates, assess demand, collect customer feedback, and analyze market conditions, enabling a comprehensive assessment of the effectiveness of pricing and service policies.

Fig. 1. Key factors shaping the financial results of hotel enterprises in the digital environment

Source: author's development

The room fund's occupancy rate is a basic indicator that determines the volume of implementation of the leading hotel service and lays the groundwork for generating income from related services. An increase in the number of staying guests objectively expands the possibilities for offering additional services, particularly food, health, and recreational services, thereby diversifying the hotel enterprise's income structure and increasing its financial stability.

The level of accommodation prices is determined based on expected demand, market conditions, and analytical data from digital platforms. Optimizing tariffs allows hotels to balance room occupancy and profitability, ensuring stable financial results without losing customers and maintaining competitiveness.

An important factor in the formation of income from additional services is the average hotel rating, calculated from guest ratings on digital platforms. This indicator integrates an assessment of the quality of service, compliance of tariffs and service content with consumer expectations and directly affects repeat bookings and the use of related services [13, p. 93].

The generalization of these indicators underscores the need to consider the management of occupancy, tariff policy, and service levels as interrelated elements of a single revenue management system for a hotel enterprise. The integration of digital platforms for short-term rentals into these processes allows not only to increase financial performance and competitiveness, but also to effectively use digital channels for customer interaction to stimulate repeat bookings and improve the customer experience.

One of the key aspects of increasing the financial efficiency of hotel enterprises is optimizing tariff policy and applying revenue management mechanisms that take into account digital channels for customer attraction. The use of dynamic pricing on the Airbnb, Booking.com and Vrbo platforms allows hotels to quickly respond to changes in demand, seasonal fluctuations and the activity of competitors in real time, which helps to maximize revenue from core services and

stimulates additional sales of related services, such as restaurants, spa treatments and excursions [14].

The integration of digital booking channels and marketing communications with the revenue management system enables more accurate forecasting of customer behavior, assessment of demand flexibility, and optimization of room stock occupancy. The interaction between tariff decisions and guest perceptions creates a reputation effect that directly affects repeat bookings and overall customer satisfaction. Thus, an effective combination of tariff strategies and digital tools increases revenues, enhances the hotel's competitiveness, and ensures balanced financial results.

Key revenue management mechanisms include dynamic pricing, which adjusts tariffs based on room stock occupancy, season, and demand on digital booking channels. Using this tool allows hotels to optimize revenue from core services, minimize periods of low occupancy, and increase average revenue per guest [15].

Customer base segmentation is another crucial element of hotel revenue management. Grouping guests by booking frequency, price sensitivity, and preferences for additional services allows to create personalized rate packages and special offers. This increases customer loyalty, encourages additional spending on related services, and reduces churn.

The use of online bookings, mobile applications, social networks, and hotel rating systems enables to respond to changes in demand quickly, adjust rates in real time, analyze the effectiveness of advertising campaigns, and predict customer behavior. The relationship between tariff policy, occupancy rate and customer perception forms a complex effect on financial results and guest satisfaction [16, p. 11].

At the same time, studying the application of tariff strategies and revenue management mechanisms allows to identify key factors that limit the full integration

of digital channels into hotel operations. These include organizational barriers (insufficient internal expertise and lack of integrated management processes), financial constraints (limited budget for digital tools and marketing channels) and regulatory barriers (restrictions on online bookings and tax accounting rules), which can hinder the use of platforms to increase occupancy rate and optimize hotel revenues [17].

Table 1 presents the main types of constraints, their impact on hotel operations, and possible ways to overcome them. This generalization allows us to identify priority areas for integrating digital channels to develop a balanced financial and service hotel strategy.

Table 1

Main organizational, financial and regulatory constraints to integrating digital channels into hotel operations

Barriers	Impact	Possible ways to overcome
Organizational	Insufficient level of staff qualifications to work with online platforms; lack of internal procedures for integrating digital channels	Conducting training programs, developing operational process standards, and delegating responsibility for digital channels
Financial	High costs of integrating IT solutions and platform commissions; limited marketing budget	Optimizing costs, using packaged solutions, attracting partner programs and grants
Regulatory	Absence or ambiguity of legislative norms regarding short-term rentals and online bookings; tax restrictions	Interaction with authorities, compliance with licensing and tax requirements, participation in industry associations to formulate regulatory proposals

Source: author's own development

Analysis of Table 1 allows us to conclude that organizational, financial and regulatory barriers have a complex impact on the efficiency of hotel operations. For example, low staff qualifications and the lack of standardized procedures for integrating digital channels (organizational barriers) can lead to inefficient use of financial resources and additional training and IT system adaptation costs (financial

constraints). Regulatory barriers, in particular unclear or contradictory requirements for short-term rentals, limit hotels' ability to implement optimal tariff strategies, use online booking platforms, and attract new customer segments. At the same time, the use of digital platforms such as Airbnb and Booking.com partially compensates for these limitations through dynamic pricing tools, demand analytics, and personalized offers.

Thus, the effective integration of digital short-term rental platforms into hotel operations requires the comprehensive use of analytical and management tools to respond promptly to market changes. Segmenting the customer base by booking frequency, price sensitivity, and preferences for additional services enables to create personalized tariff packages and special offers. Using this data, along with CRM systems and digital marketing channels, increases guest loyalty, creating long-term advantages for hotels in the services market.

Integration of digital booking channels and marketing communications ensures coordination between direct sales and online bookings, allowing to optimize platform commission costs, increase room stock occupancy, and improve the customer experience. Using the TripAdvisor and Google Hotels platforms to collect reviews and ratings contributes to the formation of a positive reputation effect.

At the same time, regular professional development and standardization of internal protocols for working with platforms allow staff to quickly adapt to market changes and maintain a high level of service, develop effective interaction with digital channels, reduce the time for processing customer requests and improve the quality of service.

Active interaction between hospitality management, regulatory authorities and industry associations enables consideration of legislative and tax requirements, minimizes legal risks, and ensures the legitimacy of digital transactions, thereby creating the prerequisites for the safe expansion of digital channels of interaction and the stable development of the hotel business.

The implementation of these measures will create conditions for comprehensive management of revenues and expenses, combining financial efficiency with improved customer service and contributing to the hotel's stable, competitive market positioning.

Conclusions. The study shows that integrating digital platforms into traditional hotels' operations significantly affects revenue generation, customer experience management, and market positioning. Analysis of the interaction between accommodation facilities and online services such as Airbnb, Booking.com, and Tripadvisor allowed us to identify key mechanisms by which digital channels influence room stock occupancy, the share of income from additional services, and guest satisfaction.

The effectiveness of tariff strategies and revenue management mechanisms is examined, accounting for the peculiarities of digital customer engagement. It is found that the use of differentiated tariffs, dynamic pricing, and coordination of direct and online booking channels helps optimize financial results and increase hotel competitiveness.

It has been established that organizational, financial and regulatory constraints remain significant barriers to the integration of digital platforms. Eliminating these obstacles through standardization of internal processes, personnel training, and adaptation to legislative requirements provides the conditions for the full use of the potential of online services and improving the quality of service.

Implementation of comprehensive measures will enable effective management of revenues and expenses, balance the development of the service offer, and ensure a sustainable market positioning for hotels.

Prospects for further research are to study the optimal models of interaction between digital and traditional channels in different segments of the hotel business, to assess the long-term impact of digital platforms on the financial stability of

enterprises, and to analyze the effectiveness of personalized tariff strategies for building customer loyalty in the face of growing digital competition.

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